

WORK-LIFE BALANCE AMONG THE WOMEN EMPLOYEES IN BANKING SECTOR OF BANGLADESH: A STUDY ON SELECTED PRIVATE COMMERCIAL BANKS IN DHAKA CITY

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Abstract

This study was conducted among the women employees of different private commercial banks of Dhaka City to find out the perception and impact of work-life balance. A total number of 91 women employees were selected by using Cochran's formula from different private commercial banks in Dhaka City on a random sampling basis. A structured questionnaire was sent to them for their responses and suggestions. The study found that the respondents are dissatisfied with their working hours, traveling time to work and reach home, lack of day care center for children to look after, lack of proper implementation of work life balance policy in the organization. The study concluded that for the betterment of both employee and organization, the work-life balance policy should be implemented in the organization and should be followed strictly. If the issues like flexible working hour, travelling hours to work, attending in social programs, children's care system etc. are attained properly the performance of the employees will boost up which will ultimately be beneficial to the organizational development.

Keywords: Work-life balance (WLB); Working environment; Working hour; Flexible work schedule; Family.

Introduction

The banking industry of a country works for the financial stability and sourcing funds to the economy. Banking industry is one of the fastest growing industries in Bangladesh, where both public and private banks are operating their business. Especially, the private banks are generating a huge number of job opportunities where a remarkable number of female employees are engaged in their professional lives as a banker. To ensure smooth operations and to develop bank industry, well trained, well-groomed and emotionally balanced workers are needed. A poor balance between an employees' work commitments and their other responsibilities can lead to stress, high absenteeism, and low productivity (Narayana and Neelima, 2017)

In general, the women of our country maintain the house hold works. Due to the expansion of economy and business activities, the women are participating in work field and have been engaged with their professional lives much more than before. Work-life balance entails attaining equilibrium between professional work and other activities, so that it reduces conflict between official and personal life (Clarke et. al. 2004). But increasing work pressures, globalization and technical advancement have impact on balancing professional and personal life (Delecta, 2011). These are also affecting the social, psychological, economic and mental well-being of an individual.

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All these being reflected in the output of an individual which affects one's performance.

The competition for market leadership in the banking industry in Bangladesh the management is giving excessive work load to meet up the targets. For this reason, the women employees are in extreme pressure. The women employees need to notice the facts like working hours, distance of work place and working environment (kumari, 2012) so that she can easily manage the house hold works too. But in our country specially in banking sector it is found that most of the banks have lacking proper WLB policy (Tabassum et. al. 2011). Absence of proper policy and poor implementation of life balance policies in the organization may bring broken or unhappy home and poor social life of women (Fapohunda, 2014).

Now a day the management has realized the importance of WLB of their employees and they are trying to set up innovative policies so that the women can maintain the balance and can make a proper policy regarding employees' work-life balance issues.

Objectives of the Study

The present study has been conducted with a view to achieving the following specific objectives:

- to identify the factors relating work-life balance among the working women in private commercial banks in Dhaka City;
- to examine the perception about the work-life balance among the working women in private commercial banks of Bangladesh; and
- to provide suggestions for the improvement of the work-life balance among women employees in private sector banking in Bangladesh in light of the findings of the present study.

Limitations of the Study

The study needs to consider the following limitations:

- The employees hesitate to disclose the facts for security reasons;
- There is no measure to explore the fact whether the information provided by the respondents are correct or not; and
- The study is based on the perception of the employees which may change over the time.

Review of Literature

The concept of WLB was coined in America in 1986. The issue involved a special attention from academics, practitioners, businesses, government agencies, trade unions, media and the public opinion (Harris & Foster, 2008). Singh (2013) speculates that the issue of work-life balance has grown in popularity as it stood for a crucial driver for societal prosperity and fulfillment and growth of every worker and every company. An extended work-life balance concept was developed that focused

on the equilibrium between one's private life and work, for all workers independent of family status (Hyman et al., 2003).

Lazăr et al. (2010) point out that WLB should not be seen as devoting equal amounts of time to paid work and non-paid roles; in its broader sense, it should be associated with a satisfactory level of involvement or "fit" between the multiple roles in a person's life.

According to Greenhaus et al. (2003), WLB consists of time balance, involvement balance, and satisfaction balance. According to Frone (2003), in turn, work-family balance consists of work-family conflict and work-family facilitation (corresponding with role conflict and enhancement, respectively).

The study of individual-related variables has been undertaken by a high number of researchers who focused their attention on variables like age, gender, emotional intelligence, motivation, marital status etc. (Hyman et al., 2003; Hsieh et al., 2005; Grzywacz et al., 2007, 2008; Sjoberg, 2008; Gregory & Milner, 2012).

The family-related variables including couples' employment status, reciprocal support, parental/home responsibilities, number of children or spouse work hours have been addressed by researchers from the work-life standpoint (Guest, 2002; Frye & Breugh, 2004; Pedersen et al., 2011; Shah, 2014).

The examination of work-related variables within the work-life balance theory approaches issues like work schedule flexibility, task variety, autonomy and complexity, the number of worked hours (Hyman et al., 2007; Mayo et al., 2008; Macky and Boxall, 2008; Steiber, 2009; Vanishree, 2012; Nordenmark, Vinberg and Strandh, 2012). Mayo et al. (2008) and Macky and Boxall (2008) pointed out that working longer hours is linked to a greater work-life imbalance and that the power to act autonomously is positively correlated with work-life balance. Steiber (2009) underlined that long working hours and the necessity of working overtime positively correlates with the escalation of the work-life conflict in general, and with work-family conflict.

Due to globalization of policies and international trade it is becoming important for the economies to have highly developed banking sector. This rapid growth and expansion of banking sector has adversely affected the Work-life balance due to demanding more and more time from the employees (Khalid et al., 2005). A descriptive survey conducted by Gururaja et al. (2013) where he concluded that the work-life balance and job satisfaction are directly correlated ($r = 0.77$) where satisfaction in one's own area of work can lead to a satisfying career.

The study of Varatharaj and Vasantha (2012) was to find out the Work-life balance of working women in service sector. The findings of the study revealed that most of the women employees feel comfortable in their work place irrespective of their working environment and work place irritants.

Tabassum et al. (2011) studied the Work-life of employees of private commercial banks in Bangladesh and found that a significant difference exists between male and female employees QWL in the following factors: flexible work schedule and working environment, attention to family, and employee relations.

Another study conducted by Kumari (2012) was to find about the employee's perception of their Work-life balance policies and practices in the public-sector banks. The findings of the study emphasized that the women employees specially prioritized the issues like working hour, distance to work place, day care center, and leave policies of the organization as the indicators of job satisfaction.

According to Clarke et al. (2004), workers who have some form of control over their working environment tend to suffer less stress-related ill-health, with clear implications for the concept of work-life balance. Organizations can implement various work-life balance initiatives that may assist employees to better balance their work and family responsibilities, gain improvements in well-being and provide organizational benefits. There are a large variety of family friendly policies which include but are not limited to the following: flexible working hours, job sharing, and part-time work, compressed work weeks, parental leave, telecommuting, on-site child care facility (Hartel, 2007).

Ojo et al. (2014) investigated the concept of work-life balance policies and practices in Nigerian Banking industry. The findings reveal that there is wide gap between work-life Balance practices and employees' understanding of the concept; the study suggests some policy implications which would aid the implementation of Work-life Balance policies in the studied sectors.

Statement of the Problem

Several studies have been found on work-life balance among the employees working in banking sector around the world, but a few studies have been found on women employees working in private commercial banking sector in Dhaka City. Therefore, there is scope to explore more regarding this issue. The purpose of the study is to identify the most important factors responsible for the imbalance of WLB of women employees working in private commercial banking sector in Dhaka city.

Methodology of the Study

Sample

The present study was conducted on a sample of 91 women employees from 6 private commercial banks located in Dhaka City on a random sampling basis. The sample is normally distributed. For calculating sample size Cochran's formula has been used. The formula is as follows:

$$n_0 = \frac{z^2 pq}{e^2}$$

Where,

n_0 = the sample size;

z = the selected critical value of desired confidence level;

p = the estimated proportion of an attribute that is present in the population;

q = $1 - p$; and

e = the desired level of precision.

Assuming the maximum variability, which is equal to 50% ($p=0.5$) and taking 95% confidence level with $\pm 10\%$ precision (margin of error), the calculation for required sample size will be as follows:

$$n_0 = \frac{z^2 pq}{e^2}$$

Here, $p = 0.5$ and hence $q = 1 - 0.5 = 0.5$; $e = 0.10$; $z = 1.96$

$$n_0 = \frac{z^2 pq}{e^2} = \frac{1.96^2 \times 0.5 \times 0.5}{0.10^2} = 96.04$$

If n_0/N is negligible then n_0 is a satisfactory approximation to the sample size. But in this case, the sample size (96.04 or 97) exceeds 5% of the population size (1455). So, we need to use the correction formula to calculate the final sample size.

Here, $N = 1455$, $n_0 = 97$

$$n = \frac{n_0}{1 + \frac{n_0 - 1}{N}} = \frac{96.04}{1 + \frac{96.04 - 1}{1455}} = 90.15 \text{ or } 91$$

Therefore, a total of 91 respondents have been taken as sample.

Data Collection and Analysis

A specially designed questionnaire was constructed on the basis of literature review, taking opinion from experts and from prospective respondents. Before finalizing the questionnaire, a pilot survey was also conducted, and necessary adjustments were made. The initial reliability of the items was verified by computing the Cronbach's alpha. The Cronbach's alpha suggests that a minimum alpha of .70 is sufficient for early stage of research (Nunnally, 1978). The Cronbach's alpha estimated for all the variables was .747 (table 1). As the Cronbach's alpha was much higher than .70 the constructs were therefore deemed to have adequate reliability.

Table 1: Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.689	.747	13

Along with some open-ended questions, the questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale to cover information like demographic, workload, and WLB factors. The response for each question was coded on a scale denoted from 1 to 5 where 1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, and 5 = Strongly Agree. Secondary data were collected from several articles published in national and international journals, annual reports of respective banks, and online sources. Finally, the data were tabulated and analyzed through statistical techniques (Mean and Standard Deviation) using SPSS 20.0.

Results and Discussions

Based on the responses, results regarding respondents' demographic information, work-load information, and work-life balance are shown below:

Table 2: Demographic Information of the Respondents (n = 91)

Respondents' Age			Mean	
25-35	29	31.87%	39.57	
Between 35-45	41	45.05%		
More than 45	21	23.08%		
Respondents' Educational level				
Graduation	10	10.99%		
Post-Graduation	72	79.12%		
Others Higher Degrees	09	9.89%		
Respondents' Designations				
Lower level officer	31	34.06%		
Mid-level officer	47	51.64%		
Top level officer	13	14.30%		
Respondents' Years of experiences				
Less than 7years	34	37.36%	9.15	
8-15 years	47	51.65%		
More than 15 years	10	10.99%		
Respondents' Monthly Income Status (000's)				
25-50	24	26.37%	69.64	
50-75	32	35.16%		
75-100	20	21.98%		
More than 100	15	16.49%		
Respondents' Marital Status				
Married	73	80.22%		
Unmarried	18	19.78%		
Respondents' Spouse Profession				
Service Holder	45	61.64%		
Business and others	28	38.36%		
Respondents' Children Status				
Yes and No. of children	1	20	32.26%	68.13%
	More than 1	42	67.74%	
No children	29	31.87%		

Source: Field Survey and from Human Resource Department of respective banks

Table 2 shows the distribution of employees according to their demographic information. The study represents most of the women is between the age of 35-45 and the mean age is 39.57. A significant percentage of the employees, 79.12%, completed their post-graduation. Only a few completed their honors and higher studies, 10.99% and 9.89% respectively. The study found that 34.06% respondents working as lower level position (Lower level includes Trainee Assistant Officer, Assistant Officer, junior officer and Officer). A significant number of respondents, 51.64%, are working at middle level position (Mid-level includes Senior Officer, Executive Officer, Senior Executive/Principal Officer), and the rest of the respondents are at top level position (Top level includes employees after Mid-level position). Among the respondents 51.65% have experience of 8-15 years and the mean experience is 9.15 years. Mean monthly income of the respondents is 62.64 thousand although 26.37% earn in between 25-50 thousand per month and 16.49% earn more than 100 thousand per month. The table also shows most of the respondents 80.22% are married and the rest are unmarried. Among the married respondents 61.64% have spouses who are service holder and 38.36% engaged in

business and other professions. The study also shows 31.87% respondents have no children where 11 respondents are married. And rest of the 68.13% respondents have children.

Table 3: Workload information of the respondents (n = 91)

Working days per week		%
	5 Days	93%
	6 Days	07%
Daily working hours		
	8-10 hours	89%
	More than 10 hours	11%
Daily traveling hours to reach the workplace		
	Less than 1 hour	29%
	1-2 hours	23%
	More than 2 hours	48%
Work shifts		
	Yes	00%
	No	100%
Time spend with the children		
	Less than 2hours	36%
	2-4 hours	43%
	More than 4 hours	21%
Take care of children while working		
	Partner	5%
	In-Laws	26%
	Servants	39%
	Others	30%

Source: Field Survey

Among the women employees, 93% of women works for 5 days in a week and remaining 7% of women work for 6 days in a week mostly in Saturday. The study shows that 89% of the total respondents work for 8-10 hours in a day and the rest of the respondents works more than 10 hours a day in a banking organization where minimum working hour for a banking organization is 8 hours a day so nobody works less than 8 hours in a day. To perform their duties, they need to travel to their office where 29% of respondents take less than 1 hour, 23% of employees spend 1-2 hours and the remaining 48% take more than 2 hours to travel to their office every day. And no women employees work in a shift. To maintain Work-life a woman needs to travel to her work place which is time consuming as well as reduces her time to spend with her family which make her dependent on others to take care of her children.

The study further shows that 36% of married working women who have children spend less than 2 hours with their children, 43% spend 2-4 hours with their children where the rest 21% spend more than 4 hours with their children every day. While working in the organization 5% of women depends on partners, 26% depends on in-laws (relative by marriage), 39% depends on servants and the rest 30% depends on others (hostels, day care center etc.) to take care of their children. In any business and industrial activities, it is of utmost importance to have well trained, well-groomed and emotionally balanced workers available to take up employment challenges. Recently, it is recognized that work-life balance can lead indirectly to productivity.

Table 4: Work-life balance of the respondents

Statements	No. of Employees Responded					
	SA	A	N	D	SD	
1. I can pay my full attention towards children	17 18.6%	26 28.6%	29 31.9%	14 15.4%	05 5.5%	Agree
2. I want to have regular contact with the relatives of my family members and friends	06 6.6%	18 19.8%	14 15.4%	35 38.5%	18 19.7%	Disagree
3. I am satisfied with my working environment	12 13.2%	38 41.7%	18 19.7%	16 17.7%	07 7.7%	Agree
4. I can give my attention for urgent family or personal issues	11 12.1%	14 15.4%	13 14.3%	43 47.2%	10 10.1%	Disagree
5. My peers assist me for successfully completing my work	12 13.2%	24 26.4%	38 41.6%	09 9.9%	08 8.8%	Neutral
6. I am satisfied with the working hours of my organization	04 4.4%	11 12.1%	16 17.6%	49 53.8%	11 12.1%	Disagree
7. There is flexible work schedule to complete tasks in my organization	02 2.1%	08 8.8%	09 9.9%	51 56.1%	21 23.1%	Disagree
8. My organization have a policy to provide different types of leaves favorable to the employees	09 9.9%	28 30.8%	29 31.9%	17 18.7%	08 8.8%	Agree
9. Organization have Work-life Balance Policy	02 2.2%	13 14.3%	14 15.4%	48 52.7%	14 15.4%	Disagree
10. My organization strictly follow Work-life balance policy	00 0%	11 12.1%	13 14.3%	57 62.7%	10 10.9%	Disagree
11. I think if employees have good work-life balance the organization will be more effective and successful	29 31.9%	53 58.2%	09 9.9%	00 0%	00 0%	Agree
12. WLB policies implemented in the organization will make my job easier	12 13.2%	39 42.9%	19 20.8%	15 16.5%	06 6.6%	Agree
13. I can balance my personal life with professional life	08 8.8%	17 18.7%	11 12.1%	38 41.7%	17 18.7%	Disagree

Source: Field Survey

Table 4 shows that 18.6% of employees strongly agreed, 28.6% of total respondents agreed and 31.9% of employees remained neutral, where 15.4% of the respondents disagreed and the rest 5.5% strongly disagreed that they can pay full attention towards children. Among the total respondents 6.6% women strongly agreed that they can maintain regular contact with the relatives of my family members and friends. 19.8% agreed and 15.4% remained neutral as they could not express their opinion. 38.5% disagreed and the rest of the respondents strongly disagreed.

Favorable Working environment is must to work in an organization and in this survey 13.2% of women employees strongly agreed that they are satisfied with their working environment. 41.7% agreed and 19.7% of total respondents remained neutral. Where 17.7% disagreed and 7.7% strongly disagreed as they thought that they were not getting favorable working atmosphere. In terms of paying attention to

urgent family and personal issues majority of the respondents, 47.2%, disagreed that they can't pay attention to urgent family and personal issues. Again, 10.1% respondents strongly disagreed to this matter.

The study shows mixed responses regarding the assistance of peers in workplace. A majority, 41.6%, remained neutral, 26.4% agreed, and 13.2% strongly agreed, 9.9% disagreed, and the rest remained strongly disagreed. In terms of working hours, 4.4% of women employees strongly agreed that they are satisfied with their organization working hour. 12.1% agreed and 17.6% of total respondents remained neutral. Where 53.8% disagreed and the remaining 12.1% strongly disagreed.

The study also found that a few employees, 27.5%, enjoys flexible work schedule and rest of the respondents have to take too many tasks at a full stretch. But most of the respondents agreed that they have favorable leave policy. Among the total respondents 2.2% of women strongly agreed, 14.3% disagreed and 15.4% of the respondents were neutral. Where 52.7% disagreed and rest of the remaining 15.4% strongly disagreed as their organizations didn't have Work-life balance policy.

In the survey 31.9% of total respondents strongly agreed, 58.2% agreed and the remaining 9.9% didn't give their opinion as they remained neutral that shows having good Work-life balance help the organization to be successful and effective. As most of the organizations have no Work-life balance policy so they can not follow the Work-life balance policy. In our survey 12.1% women agreed, 14.3% didn't give their opinion and 62.7% disagreed. Where rest of the 10.9% strongly disagreed.

Table 5: Relative importance of different factors determining WLB

Statement	Mean	Std. Deviation	Ranking
1. I am satisfied with the working hours of my organization	3.72	0.82	1
2. I am satisfied with my working environment	3.62	0.99	2
3. This organization strictly follow WLB policy	3.57	1.00	3
4. I want to have regular contact with the relatives of my family members and friends	3.45	1.20	4
5. My organization have a policy to provide different types of leaves favorable to the employees	3.43	1.24	5
6. My organization has WLB policy	3.40	1.11	6
7. There is a policy to provide different leaves to the employees in my organization	2.68	1.15	7
8. I can give my full attention towards children	2.44	1.22	8
9. I can give my attention for urgent family or personal issues	2.32	1.19	9
10. WLB policies implemented in the organization make my job easier	2.21	1.13	10
11. I think if employees have good work-life balance the organization will be more effective and successful	2.09	0.97	11
12. My peers assist me for successfully completing my work	1.93	1.10	12
13. I can balance my personal life with professional life	1.78	0.61	13

Source: Field Survey

Out of the total respondents 8.8% respondents opined that they can strongly balance with their personal lives with professional lives. 18.7% of women agreed that they can also manage their Work-life where 12.1% remained neutral. Among the rest of the respondents 41.7% disagreed and 18.7% strongly disagreed as they couldn't balance their personal lives with professional lives.

The above table (table 5) shows the relative importance of different factors determining Work-life balance. The respondents' responses regarding the dimensions are ranked in order of importance. The above table shows the mean and standard deviation of the Work-life balance factors. Considering the means the most important factors the employees consider to be able for better Work-life balance are: working hour of the organization (3.72), working environment (3.62), absence of work-life balance policy (3.4) and implementation (3.57), regular contact with the relatives of my family members and friends (3.45), flexible work schedule (3.43), organization's leave policy (2.68), attention towards children (2.44), and attention for urgent family or personal issues (2.32).

The study found that women employees, to maintain WLB, consider the working hour which is consistent with previous research findings (Hyman et al. 2007; Macky and Box all, 2008; and Steiber, 2009). Besides, the respondents give importance to the working environment which is similar to the findings of the study of Tabassum et al. (2011), and Varatharaj and Vasantha (2012). Again, factors like work-life balance policy got the attention of the women employees and most of the researchers have prioritized WLB policy and its implementation (Kumari, 2012; Hartel, 2007; and Ojo et al. 2014). Regular contact with the family members and friends is also found as an important WLB factor to the respondents. Flexible work schedule is found to be an important factor which is similar to the findings of previous studies (Hyman et al., 2007 and Tabassum et al. 2011). Organization's leave policy appears as an important factor to the respondents to maintain WLB and it is consistent with findings of Hartel, (2007). The study also reveals that factors like time balance, workplace distance, number of children, and day care center would have been considered to maintain WLB and these are similar to the findings of Greenhaus et al. (2003); Guest, (2002); Frye, and Breugh, (2004); Pedersen et al. (2011); and Shah, (2014).

Major Findings

Major findings based on above results and reply of open ended questions from the respondents are as follows:

- Most of the employees are dissatisfied with their working hours and flexible work schedule because most of the working days they require to stay on duties more than said working hours;
- Respondents are highly in need of a Work-life balance policy to implement and to follow it strictly in the organization;
- Day care center for children's look after, and transportation facilities demands by the respondents;

- It becomes difficult for most of the employees to maintain contact with relatives and family friends on working days; and
- Most of the employees can't balance their work-life and family life.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Majority of the women employees felt that their job is full of stress and that is why the WLB is decreasing. Due to work-load, continuous work pressure, long working hours, and unfriendly working environment is hampering personal as well as social life. It is also perceived by most of them that all these are happening in absence of proper implementation of WLB policy. Based on the findings the following suggestions are recommended so that both the organization and the women employees can be mutually benefited:

- As the employees are highly in need of WLB policy, bank authority should immediately develop a work life balance policy and work on it;
- Leave policies would have been made more flexible for women employees considering different valid aspects like number of children they have, children's age and schooling, life partner's profession, their age and health condition, and distance of workplace etc.;
- Transportation and day care center facilities might be arranged by the organization so that travelling time takes less time by road; and
- As employees are not satisfied with working hours, flexible work schedule, and overall working environment, organizations should pay serious attention about these issues.

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